

**COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UNSTABLE SURFACE TRAINING AND
CONVENTIONAL EXERCISES ON BALANCE IN KNEE OSTEOARTHRITIS**

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LIST OF ABBREVAITION

Abbreviation	Full Description
KOA	Knee Osteoarthritis
UST	Unstable Surface Training
BBS	Berg Balance Scale
JSN	Joint Space Narrowing
KL	Kallgren-Lawrence

ABSTRACT

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is a degenerative joint disease characterized by cartilage degradation, bone remodeling, and osteophyte formation. This causes pain, muscle weakness and impaired proprioception which leads to the poor balance and increase risk of fall. Conventional exercises improve muscle strength and reduce pain while unstable surface training enhances proprioception and joint stability. The objective was to analyze the comparative effect of unstable surface training and conventional exercises on balance in patients with knee osteoarthritis. The study was randomized clinical trial involving 32 participants, aged between 45 to 60 years, who presented with unilateral or bilateral knee osteoarthritis and has been diagnosed with grade 2 knee OA according to Kellgren-Lawrence classification. Patients experiencing symptoms for more than six months was recruited. Participants was randomly assigned to two groups: Group A received unstable surface training, involving squats, sit-to- stand, forward lunges, step-ups, timed single-leg stance, and wall slides on wobble board. Group B received conventional exercises including isometric strengthening and stretching exercises for the hamstrings and quadriceps. Both interventions was administered thrice a week for four weeks. Balance was assessed using the Berg Balance scale (BBS). Assessments was conducted at baseline and post- intervention, after a four-week follow-up. Statistical analysis will be performed using SPSS version 26. Normality of data was checked and for within group comparison paired t-test was used and to compare both the groups independent t- test was used. Results showed that unstable surface training was found to be more efficient than conventional exercise program. The mean value of post BBS score of both groups was compared. Post BBS score of group A was 46.25 ± 4.64 while post BBS score of group B was 38.37 ± 4.57 with mean difference of 7.88 according to the study's findings unstable surface training is more effective in term of increasing balance in patient with knee OA.

Keywords: Berg Balance Scale, Conventional exercise program, Knee Osteoarthritis, Unstable surface training.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis is a degenerative disease characterized by cartilage degradation, bone remodeling, and osteophyte formation. This leads to clinical symptoms including pain, stiffness, swelling, and limitation in joint function. Approximately 240 million individuals have symptomatic osteoarthritis worldwide. The occurrence of knee osteoarthritis is increasing with an increase in age, BMI, and physical trauma to the knee. Around 13% of women and 10% of male aged 60 years and older are affected by knee osteoarthritis. Pain and other clinical manifestations associated with knee osteoarthritis affect the quality of life of patients by reducing functional mobility. Osteoarthritis is a chronic condition affecting not only articular cartilage but meniscus, ligament, and peri articular muscles by different pathological mechanisms (Steinmetz et al., 2023).

The largest and most intricate synovial joint in the human body is the knee joint. With a restricted amount of internal and exterior rotation, it functions as a modified hinge joint that mainly permits flexion and extension. Structurally, it is a compound joint comprising three main articulations: the medial tibiofemoral, lateral tibiofemoral and patellofemoral compartments. To improve the mechanical efficiency of the quadriceps the patella, which is embedded in the quadriceps tendon, articulates with the femoral trochlear groove. Four major ligaments play a major role in maintaining stability. the medial and lateral collateral ligaments (MCL and LCL), which resist valgus and varus pressures and the anterior and posterior cruciate ligaments (ACL and PCL), which control anterior-posterior translation and rotation. The menisci, which are crescent-shaped fibrocartilaginous structures improve joint stability and lubrication while distributing stresses and absorbing shock. Encasing the joint is the synovial membrane and fibrous capsule, which provide lubrication and reinforcement (Greco et al., 2023).

Key motions of the knee joint as a complex modified hinge joint are flexion and extension and coupled tibial internal and external rotation. Its stability results from the dynamic interaction of muscles ligaments and bone geometry. Unlike the posterior cruciate ligament (PCL), which prevents the occurrence of the posterior translation, the anterior cruciate ligament (ACL) prevents the occurrence of anterior tibial translation and rotating forces. The medial and lateral collateral ligaments (MCL and LCL) are the sources of the medial and lateral stability of the valgus and varus,

respectively. The menisci are necessary to confer joint congruity, stress absorption, and distributing loads. Locomotion against the external demands is measured by the quadriceps, hamstring and gastrocnemius muscles which support the joint against external demands. Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is typified by biomechanical changes, including adduction moment or rotational instability, which accelerate cartilage degenerative alterations and the emergence of disease (Giri & Tewari, 2024).

The development of osteoarthritis (OA) in the knee is a complicated interaction between modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors. Due to the build-up of mechanical load, cellular senescence, and a constant impairment of the regenerative capacity of joint tissues, advanced age remains the most robust predictor that remains immutable (Coryell et al., 2021). Female sex is also another risk factor that is more severe and prevalent in postmenopausal women. This is largely due to the loss of estrogen protective action to bone and cartilages. Despite genetic predisposition as a factor in the susceptibility due to its influence on the inflammatory pathways and cartilage structure environmental variables are also significant. The most significant risk factor that can be modified is probably obesity. Its role is dual-faceted it imposes excessive mechanical load on weight-bearing joints and crucially promotes a state of chronic low-grade systemic inflammation through the release of adipokines like leptin from adipose tissue which accelerate joint degradation independently of load (Wang & He, 2018).

Age, genetics, and mechanical trauma can all trigger pathophysiological mechanisms that result in osteoarthritis. The articular cartilage may soften in the early stages of a hypertrophic healing phase because of an increase in water content brought on by the loss of glycosaminoglycan (GAG). Anabolic activity and the synthesis of collagen type II and proteoglycan are elevated. Chondrocytes accelerate rate of proliferation cause them to group. The decrease of GAG content in the early stages of the disease causes changes in the tissue's osmotic pressure and cartilage compressive resistance because the mechanical properties of cartilage are sensitive to its composition and structure. These changes result in cartilage loss. Fragments of collagen type II from the injured cartilage surface can cause the synovial membrane to become inflamed. Degradation of cartilage may be encouraged by inflammatory mediators generated by an irritated synovium (Luyten et al., 2018).

One important pathological characteristic that sets osteoarthritic joints apart from healthy aging cartilage is the enzymatic activity present in them. Agrecanases such

ADAMTS-4 and ADAMTS-5, as well as matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs) especially MMP-13 are significantly elevated in osteoarthritis (OA). These enzymes have a major role in the faster breakdown of collagen and aggrecan the primary structural components of articular cartilage. The increased enzyme activity upsets the balance between synthesis and breakdown leading to increased matrix loss and reduced joint biomechanical integrity. However, in age-matched non-OA cartilage these enzymes are either absent or present at baseline physiological levels. These levels reflect the normal homeostatic turnover of the extracellular matrix, which maintains cartilage function without resulting in structural deterioration (Yang et al., 2017).

Pro-inflammatory cytokines, particularly Interleukin-1 beta (IL-1 β) and Tumor Necrosis Factor-alpha (TNF- α) are released when the synovium becomes inflamed (synovitis). These cytokines accelerate the breakdown of cartilage by further stimulating chondrocytes to manufacture more catabolic enzymes. They also have a role in joint effusion and discomfort (Scanzello & Goldring, 2012). In OA, the subchondral bone underlying the cartilage is extremely active. The subchondral plate sclerosis (hardening) is caused by increased bone turnover and remodeling. Visible on MRI bone marrow lesions (BMLs) are regions of necrosis, fibrosis, and edema that are strongly linked to pain. A failed attempt at repair, osteophytes (bone spurs) develop at the edges of joints frequently resulting in pain and mechanical restrictions on joint motion (Barr, 2016).

Balance is an important indicator of physical function and risk of falling. The capacity to keep the center of mass near the base of support is known as balance. It involves the interplay of proprioceptive sensory inputs vestibular and visual systems motor systems including muscle activity and strength and cognitive elements. Many functional activities involve balancing which also helps prevent falls. In addition to being one of the main reasons why older adults are admitted to hospitals worse balance function is linked to a higher risk of falling which can result in fractures joint dislocations soft-tissue injuries loss of independence and death (Etherton-Beer et al., 2023).

In people with osteoarthritis (OA) knee balance impairment is a complex problem that results from a complex interaction between neurological and physiological deficiencies. The primary reason is proprioceptive dysfunction which occurs when damage to mechanoreceptors inside the damaged joint, synovium and ligaments impairs the central nervous system's perception of joint position and movement. This warped signal

causes imperfect sensorimotor control by delaying the onset of corrective muscle responses to postural sway. By inducing arthrogenic muscular inhibition. The reflexive contraction of the surrounding muscles particularly the quadriceps pain makes this issue worse. Because of this inhibition the main stabilizers around the knee and hip become much weaker and the force and velocity of the muscle contractions required to maintain balance are also decreased (Kim et al., 2018).

Furthermore, structural changes that impair normal biomechanics and reduce the base of support during stance and walking include flexion contractures, effusion, and joint instability. Patients have a tight and cautious walking pattern that they use to balance the pain and the instability, and this ironically takes away the normal muscle activity and ankle movement needed to restore dynamic balance. Lastly, the fear of falling prevalent among this population group makes them more cautious and avoids behavior that further deconditions the neuromuscular apparatus and develops a vicious cycle of deterioration. This combined reduction in sensory input, motor output and biomechanical functionality is highly dangerous to falls and functional limitation (Zeng et al., 2022).

Compared to people without knee OA patients with the condition usually suffer weakening in their quadriceps muscles or impaired proprioception within the joint. These disease-related limitations could account for these patients' worse balances. In people with medial knee OA standing balance was predicted by knee alignment knee pain intensity, quadriceps strength, and disease severity (Park et al., 2013). Because KOA patients have trouble balancing, they must maintain knee stability to avoid unintentional injuries from falls Lack of proprioceptive feeling in KOA patients results in non-physiological joint loads and gradual progressive joint deterioration. These individuals also show altered muscular-activation patterns and decreased muscle strength especially in the quadriceps muscles, which may account for their poor balance (Liu et al., 2017).

Around the world osteoarthritis (OA) is a prevalent and incapacitating ailment. Of these knee OA (KOA) makes up a significant percentage and presents with several symptoms that impair quality of life, including pain, stiffness, dysfunction, and even deformity. To diagnose KOA imaging methods are combined with a brief physical examination and symptom evaluation. While conventional radiography is commonly used to assess the Kallgren-Lawrence (KL) composite score magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is usually used to assess the cartilage, synovium, and subchondral bone abnormalities. The

assessment of therapeutic efficacy is mostly reliant on clinical and frequently rater-dependent results because contemporary treatment of KOA heavily depends on the identification of clinical information (Lv et al., 2021).

Despite being created more than 50 years ago the Kallgren-Lawrence (KL) grading system is still the most widely used radiographic tool for identifying and classifying the degree of osteoarthritis (OA) in the knee. A weight-bearing anteroposterior radiograph is necessary for the diagnosis using the KL score to precisely measure joint space narrowing under load. Osteophytes joint space constriction, subchondral sclerosis, and bony deformity are the main characteristics that determine the system's grade, which ranges from 0 to 4. There are no features in Grade 0, definite osteophytes with possible JSN are present in Grade 1 (doubtful), definite osteophytes with possible JSN are present in Grade 2 (minimal), definite JSN, multiple osteophytes, and some sclerosis are present in Grade 3, and severe JSN, large osteophytes, marked sclerosis, and definite bony deformity are present in Grade 4 (Kalpana & Kumar, 2023).

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)-based grading methods are used in further confined imaging to assess osteoarthritis. The most often used of these are the MRI Osteoarthritis Knee Score (MOAKS) and the Whole Organ Magnetic Resonance Imaging Score (WORMS). Comparing these technologies to traditional imaging techniques they are thought to be more detailed. They make a variety of joint structures visible such as bone marrow lesions, cartilage, menisci, and synovium. Clinicians can identify minor pathological changes that simple radiographs would overlook thanks to this thorough evaluation. Because of its high sensitivity MRI-based grading is especially helpful in detecting osteoarthritis in its early stages. These techniques also provide useful information for monitoring the course of an illness over time. Consequently, they play a significant role in both clinical decision-making and research applications (Javed et al., 2021).

A thorough multimodal and patient-centered strategy that considers comorbidities, functional limits, symptom severity, and personal preferences is the foundation of the modern care of osteoarthritis (OA) in the knee. Reducing pain, improving joint function, raising general quality of life, and, if possible, slowing the progression of the disease are the main objectives of treatment. First line management places a strong emphasis on non-pharmacological approaches such as weight loss for overweight people which lessens the mechanical load and metabolic strain on the joints, land-based and aquatic exercise therapy to strengthen muscles, improve proprioception, and maintain

mobility, and structured patient education and self-management programs to promote active participation. Neuromuscular training and balance exercises are frequently used in physical therapy to treat instability (Kolasinski et al., 2020).

Several pharmacological alternatives topical NSAIDs combined with sporadic intra-articular injections of hyaluronic acid or corticosteroids offer a fair trade-off between risk and benefit for chronic pain management. Mild to moderate KOA may also benefit from topical capsaicin. It has not been demonstrated that acetaminophen works well as an analgesic. Because opioids especially tramadol have strong adverse effects that outweigh their advantages each case needs to be considered separately. Duloxetine a serotonin-norepinephrine reuptake inhibitor may be a systemic alternative for people whose pain persists and is difficult to control despite these treatments. When conservative therapy fails to alleviate significant pain and disability in patients with advanced end-stage OA surgery especially total knee arthroplasties is a highly successful treatment option (Lim & Al-Dadah, 2022).

Traditional exercise regimen for improving balance in people with osteoarthritis (OA) in the knee are fundamental and concentrate on strengthening the lower extremities, improving neuromuscular control and improving functional stability through a sequence of progressive land-based exercises. Strength training for the quadriceps, hamstrings, hip abductors, and extensors muscles essential for preserving dynamic joint stability and shock absorption during weight-bearing activities is usually incorporated into these regimens. To develop this strength exercises like step-ups, mini-squats, and straight leg raises are frequently recommended. These exercises are intended to enhance postural techniques encourage co-contraction of stabilizer muscles and improve proprioceptive acuity (Wang et al., 2025).

To achieve balance in the osteoarthritis (OA) knee patient with unstable surface neuromuscular training (UST) is a purposely altered training surface that challenges the sensorimotor system. In this technique the device involves the creation of a dynamic unpredictable environment, like inflated stability cushions, foam pads, wobble boards, and balancing discs, to perform exercises. UST majorly increases the proprioceptive demand by making the muscles to adjust constantly, unconsciously, to stabilize the body. This enhances reactive, postural control and joint position awareness as well as co-contraction of stabilizing muscles surrounding the knee, hip, and core (Ershad et al., 2022).

UST is used to stimulate neuromuscular activity in patients with knee OA who tend to have pronounced proprioceptive deficits and quadriceps inhibition as a result of pain

and joint degradation. Exercises tend to start with bilateral positions over softer surfaces, to unilateral positions and moving positions of various difficulty machines, so that a gradual process of adaptation is ensured. Studies show that UST is more effective in enhancing balance than usual training on a stable surface since it treats neuromuscular weaknesses that make this group unsteady. A recent randomized controlled study has demonstrated that UST particularly improved dynamic balance and functional performance in knee OA patients which made it a value state-of-the-art rehabilitation technique (Behm et al., 2015).

Balance training is used to assist individuals with knee osteoarthritis (KOA) to balance their bodies and enhance their proprioception that is frequently lower because of joint degeneration. It enhances better awareness of the position of the joints because the sensory receptors are re-trained around the knee. Moreover, this kind of training enhances knee position and stability by developing the major muscles that stabilize the knee such as the quadriceps. Balance exercises improve neuromuscular control that improves coordination and faster muscle contractions. The effects of these changes are decreased risk of falls and enhanced functional activities such as walking and climbing stairs. Also, increased balance encourages increased consistency in joint loading that can limit the load on the injured knee. Stabilization allows patients to become more assured and to fear falling less (Elsheikh et al., 2020).

1.1. Problem Statement

Knee osteoarthritis impairs balance, and proprioception, thus increasing risk of fall. Both conventional exercises and unstable surface training improves these deficits. However, studies comparing their effects on balance in knee OA are scarce making it essential to identify the most effective approach for rehabilitation.

i. Rationale

Although rehabilitation programs frequently incorporate conventional exercises. However, unstable surface training has drawn interest due to its potential to improve neuromuscular control and proprioceptive feedback. To improve management options for people with knee osteoarthritis, this study aims to find out which approach delivers the greatest improvements in postural control and functional balance.

1.2. Research Objectives

To determine the comparative efficacy of unstable surface training and a conventional

exercise on balance in knee osteoarthritis.

1.3. Research Questions

What is the difference between the effects of unstable surface training and conventional exercises on balance in knee osteoarthritis?

Hypothesis

Alternative Hypothesis (H_1):

There is no significant difference between the effects of unstable surface training and conventional exercises on balance in knee osteoarthritis.

Null Hypothesis (H_0):

There is significant difference between the effects of unstable surface training and conventional exercises on balance in knee osteoarthritis.

Chapter 2

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Knee osteoarthritis (OA) is a common degenerative condition causing pain, stiffness, and balance issues. Strengthening and flexibility exercises are common components of conventional therapy. Unstable surface training has drawn interest lately due to its ability to enhance balance and proprioception. The relative efficacy of unstable surface training and conventional exercise is examined in this review of literature.

A systematic review Studied Physical therapies for improving balance and reducing fall risk in osteoarthritis. 15 randomized controlled trials totaling 1482 people were included in the study; the mean PeDro score of 7 indicated good methodological quality. With a pooled standardized mean difference of 0.3346 (95% CI: 0.3207-0.60; $P < 0.00001$; $I^2 = 0\%$), strength training was consistently found to significantly enhance balance. With an SMD of 0.7597 (95% CI: 0.5130-1.2043), Tai Chi showed significantly more advantages, emphasizing its potent fall prevention effect. In older persons with knee OA, aerobic workouts have also been shown to enhance balance and lower the risk of falls. Conversely, there were no appreciable gains from light treatment or water-based exercises. These results offer compelling proof that aerobic workouts, Tai Chi, and strength training are useful methods for improving balance. These kinds of interventions can be suggested as useful and realistic fall prevention strategies. Overall rehabilitation programs for people with knee OA should incorporate physical therapy that emphasize on balance (Mat et al., 2014).

A Systematic Review and to assess the Effects of Strength Training Using Unstable Surfaces on Strength, Power and Balance Performance Across the Lifespan is administer. Three studies involving older people and fifteen involving young adults were found. In contrast to CON, STU had no moderate impacts on older people's maximum strength and medium effects on young adults. Adolescents and young adults also showed significant effects on strength endurance, whereas older people showed only a slight effect. When it comes to enhancing muscle strength, power, and balance in teenagers, young adults, and older adults, STU works better than CON. However, when the specific effects of STU were compared with those of STS, conflicting results were especially observed in young adults and adolescents. The study concludes that the performance of STU compared with STS has limited extra effects on muscle strength, power, and balance performance in healthy adolescents (Behm et al., 2015).

Patients with knee (OA) are more likely to fall, and one of the main contributing factors has been found to be impaired standing balance. The objective of the systematic review was to assess impairment throughout disease severity and compare standing balance in patients with knee OA to that of healthy individuals. Eight papers out of 2716 that were found through a thorough literature search across four major databases satisfied the inclusion and quality requirements. On common balance tests, such as the Step Test, Single-Leg Stance, Functional Reach, Tandem Stance, and the Community Balance and Mobility Scale, results consistently showed that people with knee OA performed worse than controls. With a pooled standardized mean difference of -1.64 (95% CI: $-2.58, -0.69$), the OA group's balance was noticeably worse. There were no variations between unilateral and bilateral OA or across malalignment levels. Crucially, no research explicitly contrasted with OA severity which limited understanding of the deterioration in balance associated with progression. These findings demonstrate that individuals with knee OA clearly have a balanced disadvantage. Using straightforward clinically useful assessments, further research is required to examine balance impairment across disease stages (Hatfield et al., 2016).

People with knee osteoarthritis (OA) frequently have problems with both dynamic and static balance with dynamic balance being more severely impacted. This study assessed the impact of patient education and a structured group exercise program for the lower extremities on dynamic balance as determined by the Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT). For six weeks 19 participants in experimental pilot research attended weekly sessions under supervision in addition to prescribed at-home activities. Pre- and post-intervention functional outcomes, hip and knee muscle strength, pain, and SEBT were measured. After 14 participants had finished the intervention, the dynamic balance of the affected side was significantly better both in the anterior position ($p = 0.02$) and the medial position ($p = 0.01$). Balance on contralateral side significantly improved in the anterior direction ($p = 0.001$) but the medial direction did not yield significant changes ($p = 0.07$). Also, there were significant improvements in functional evaluations, discomfort and hip and knee strength ($p < 0.05$). These results indicate that knee OA patients can take advantage of an exercise program to improve the dynamics of balance (Al-Khlaifat et al., 2016).

To find out how physical therapy can help individuals with knee osteoarthritis (OA) to balance themselves and decrease their risk of falling, a randomized controlled experiment is being carried out. The participants of the study will be recruited among

individuals that are highly vulnerable to falls or fall within the past year and aged between 60 to 90 years. A rigorous physiological and functional assessment will be performed on each participant that will involve the proprioception, balance, lower limb strength, and executive functional tests. The main aim of the intervention will be the customized physical therapy exercises that will optimize the stability and functional performance. The purpose of the study is to determine the safest and most effective exercise programs to decrease the risk of fall in this at-risk population. It is believed that the findings will be useful in offering clinicians information that will help them treat the balance issues of patients who experience knee OA. In the future, more comprehensive clinical trial designs will also be based on the results. Ultimately, the proposed study will guide older persons with knee OA to live quality lives and devise fall prevention strategies (Levinger et al., 2017).

The aim of the study was to evaluate the effects of low-intensity exercise programs based on lower extremity either at home or by supervision on hemodynamic parameters, muscular strength, pain, and balance in patients with osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee. A total of 78 patients were randomized to one of two groups; one group participated in group activities under clinical supervision, while the other group was instructed to practice the same exercises independently at home. Before and after the six-week intervention, tests were performed to determine non-invasive hemodynamic parameters, discomfort, quadriceps and hamstring muscular strength, and the six-minute walk test (6MWT). Of the 78 participants, 56 completed the study. Both groups showed notable gains in 6MWT performance, muscle strength, and pain reduction. But in addition to notable improvements in balance ($p = 0.009$), the supervised group had noticeably larger improvements in pain ($p = 0.041$), quadriceps strength (right: $p = 0.009$, left: $p = 0.013$), and right hamstring strength ($p = 0.04$). Hemodynamic parameters did not significantly alter in either group. Overall, the results show that supervised clinical programs are more successful in lowering post-activity pain and improving muscular strength and balance in individuals with knee OA, even if both supervised and home-based low-intensity exercise programs are helpful (Kuru Çolak et al., 2017).

Patients with osteoarthritis (OA) frequently experience knee instability, which is frequently accompanied by pain. The impact of balance exercises on knee instability and pain severity was examined in this randomized controlled experiment. Thirty knee OA patients were randomized to either the control group which received ultrasound, TENS, and hot pack therapy, or the balancing exercise group. For three weeks, both

groups received treatment five times a week. A Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) questionnaire measuring pain intensity and instability (buckling, shifting, giving way) was used to measure the results both before and after treatment. Both groups experienced notable increases, according to the results, although the balancing exercise group saw the biggest gains. In the balancing group, pain scores dropped from 6.53 to 4.60, while in the control group, they dropped from 7.46 to 5.40. A substantial difference favoring balance training was found by inter-group analysis. Overall, individuals with knee OA experienced less discomfort and improved knee instability when using balance exercises as opposed to traditional methods (Ashtiani et al., 2018).

The effect of exercise on balance and functional outcomes of patients with knee osteoarthritis (OA) was also investigated in a randomized controlled experiment. OA patients without intervention OA patients with symptoms and asymptomatic OA patients were formed into three groups. The intervention groups were exposed to an 8-week fitness program, but the control group did not get anything. Functional performance and balance measures were conducted before and after the intervention. In both the symptomatic and the asymptomatic group that exercised the results revealed a significant balance improvement and a significant reduction in the risk of falling also. Symptomatic patients experienced the exercise as less painful indicating that their functional tolerance had improved. Functional activities which included the Step Up/Over test indicated significant improvements on the asymptomatic patients. There was, however, no significant improvement in the control group. These findings suggest that individuals with knee OA can gain health benefits through exercise interventions that enhance functional and pain relief outcomes and enhance balance and reduce the risk of falls (Braghin et al., 2018).

Balance training and physical modalities were studied in a randomized clinical trial to determine how effective they are in the management of knee osteoarthritis (OA). The sample size of the study was 60 individuals having primary knee OA at the average age of 56.50 years old. The study was carried out in a single-blind design with participants in two random groups. Group A was exposed to ultrasound, TENS and standard exercise therapy, and Group B was exposed to conventional physiotherapy and Biodex Balance System (BBS)-assisted balance training. The trial-time consisted of both treatments, the results of which were evaluated as balance performance and fall risk. The findings proved that both groups showed that the gains of Group B in

terms of fall risk and balance stability were significantly higher. These results indicate that the integration of balance training based on Biodex training in physiotherapy programs is of an additional advantage. Balance focused interventions can thus be considered as a vital part of OA rehabilitation especially among the older adults who are susceptible to instability and falls (Jahanjoo et al., 2019).

The most prevalent chronic joint disease is osteoarthritis (OA) which is mainly in the knee and is linked to progressive degeneration, loss of function and proprioceptive impairments. The aim of the research was to assess the efficacy of balance training in management of mild to moderate osteoarthritis. Sixty patients with primary knee OA were recruited and randomly divided into two groups: Group I was treated with strength training and a balance training program (BSS-SD) and Group II received only strength training. The two groups trained three times in 12 weeks. Some of the evaluations included postural stability measurements, stiffness, range of motion, chair stand test, WOMAC, and pain (VAS, Ritchies scale). The outcome revealed that range of motion, stiffness, pain, and physical functioning of both groups had considerably improved. Other stability and balance measures such as fall risk and stability constraints also improved. Nevertheless, Group I exhibited a significantly greater benefit than Group II. I found that mild to moderate knee OA patients did not have a clinical and functional advantage when they used strength training compared to balance training, and in combination, this training (Elsheikh et al., 2020).

The Armed Forces Institute of Rehabilitation Medicine in Rawalpindi carried out a randomized controlled trial to determine the impact of a balance training program, Biodex, on functional performance, balance, pain, and proprioception of people with osteoarthritis in their knees. The sealed envelope method was used to assign 48 patients aged between 35 and 65 with bilateral knee OA randomly to a group of two with equal numbers. The experimental group was given a Biodex balance training combined with traditional exercises as opposed to the control group that was to be given a traditional exercise program. Efforts were made to conduct assessments at baseline and post-intervention Both groups were significantly improved over the baseline ($p < 0.05$). But anteroposterior stability as a whole stability and pain intensity improved more in the experimental group ($p < 0.05$). The study findings depict that Biodex balance training is more effective than an exclusive exercise at enhancing functional performance, stability and proprioception in individuals with knee OA. It decreases influence and unease as well (Javed et al., 2021).

A randomized assessment measured the impact of balance training on functional outcomes of the patients with osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee. The purpose was to determine the effectiveness of balance exercises to improve therapeutic outcomes of this population. Electronic databases were reviewed between January 1990 and June 2021 and the studies quality was evaluated by two reviewers. The review had 15 qualifying papers. The advantages of the trade-offs between strengthening the knee stability and functionality through training the hamstring and the quadriceps have been a focus of many studies. The combined results showed that balance training had pronounced therapeutic benefits to individuals with knee OA. General motor control, functional balance, and postural stability were the areas most improved. Balance training experimental groups made more progress as compared to control groups. The results indicate that balance training is a positive intervention, and it needs to be viewed as an essential part of the rehabilitation process of individuals with knee OA (Pirayeh et al., 2022).

An in-depth study was undertaken where pain and functional outcomes of osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee were evaluated in relation to balance training. In the process of the assessment, there was substantial evidence to endorse the substantial benefits of incorporating basic balance training as a part of rehabilitation efforts. Balance training has been established to enhance physical performance, reduce pain and encourage more exercising. Such enhancements not only make movement easier, but also decrease the chances of falling, but also boost self-confidence during movement. Balance activities were also associated with the general quality of life improvements. The findings indicate that even the simplest balance training program can be of clinical benefit to patients with knee OA. This shows how balance training should be viewed as a key component of conservative management plans. Finally balancing training is a safe, practical and effective method that supplements the traditional exercise and rehabilitation interventions on individuals with knee OA (Prabhakar et al., 2023).

Loss of proprioception and balance issues are frequent in patients with osteoarthritis (OA) in their knees. It was a randomized trial aiming to assess the outcomes of balance exercises and proprioception on patients aged 40-70 with knee OA and were female. A total of 99 patients were enrolled and assigned to an isometric strengthening, Biodex training or conventional balance training group. The groups were engaged in physical activity over a period of 10 weeks. Some of the evaluated outcomes included quality of life, the physical, pain, and dynamic balance. Results show that the Biodex training group was better than other groups in terms of overall stability index and sensory

interaction balancing scores. Pain was significantly reduced in all groups with classical balance training outperforming the control group. According to the study's findings, proprioception and balancing exercises can enhance dynamic balance and lessen pain (Ince et al., 2023).

RESEACRH GAP

Most of the current research on osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee focuses on conventional rehabilitation techniques such as strength and mobility training. Despite their advantages, these methods frequently fail to considerably enhance proprioception and dynamic balance. Because it focuses on neuromuscular control, unstable surface training (UST) is becoming a viable substitute. The results of rehabilitation for knee OA that are particular to balance are likewise not given enough attention. Static and dynamic balance are still important but rarely discussed components of OA treatment. It is necessary to directly compare UST with conventional exercises for improving balance. This disparity emphasizes the necessity of carefully planned research to direct evidence-based treatments.

Chapter 3

MATERIALS AND METHODS / METHODOLOGY

3.1. Materials and Methods

i. Research Design

The study was Randomized Clinical Trial (RCT).

ii. Study Setting

The study was conducted in Bakhtawar Amin Memorial Trust Hospital Multan due to enough eligible patients who meet the inclusion criteria for clinical trial (Friedman et al., 2015).

iii. Target Population

The target population was patients aged 45 to 60 years clinically diagnosed with knee osteoarthritis for more than 6 months.

iv. Study Duration

The total study duration was 4 months after the acceptance of the synopsis.

v. Sample Size

The calculated sample size for this study is 32 participants, based on G*Power analysis using a power of 95 %, a significance level (α) of 0.05, and a confidence interval (CI) of 95%, derived from previous studies evaluating balance as an outcome using the BBS (Kaur, 2022).

vi. Sampling Technique

Non-probability convenience sampling was used as this technique is quick, inexpensive and convenient. Participants was enrolled according to their availability and accessibility (Elifi & Negida, 2017).

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 45 to 60 years (Fawzy et al., 2025).
- Both male and female patients.
- Unilateral or bilateral knee pain.
- Pre-diagnosed, Grade 2 knee O.A patients according to Kellgren-Lawrence classification.
- Pain duration of more than 6 months (Koch et al., 2022).

Exclusion Criteria

- History of hip surgery or fracture (Koch et al., 2022).
- Morbid Obesity or having > 40 gram/meter square BMI.
- Knee synovitis or tendinitis.
- Secondary osteoarthritis.
- Receiving any intra-articular injection or physiotherapy session.

vii. Data Collection Tools

Berg Balance Scale was used (Downs, 2015).

Berg Balance Scale:

In 1989, the Berg Balance Scale was created to assess elderly people's balance. One A higher score denotes better balance. The scale has 14 components with scores ranging from 0 to 4, which are summed to create a total score between 0 and 56. The tasks range in difficulty from standing on one leg to sitting in a chair. Completing the Berg Balance Scale takes roughly ten to fifteen minutes. The Berg Balance Scale has a high relative reliability, with inter-rater reliability estimated at 0.97 and intra-rater reliability estimated at 0.98.

0-20= High risk of fall/Wheelchair bound.

21- 40 = moderate risk of fall/Walking with assistance.

>41= Low risk of fall/Independent (Tirasci et al., 2024).

viii. Data Collection Procedure

The single blind RCT study occurred within hospital parameters as researchers follow pre-established patient selection guidelines for treating knee osteoarthritis patients. The participants approved treatment by signing consent forms before beginning with the treatment plan. The study initiation required participants to receive thorough examinations together with assessments for age demographics and gender characteristics and occupational status and past medical histories. This study divided patients into two distinct groups where random selection occurred by using the lottery technique. The patients were divided into Group A requiring treatment with unstable surface training and Group B Conventional exercise program for a period of 3 days per week across 4 consecutive weeks.

The outcome variable for Balance in knee osteoarthritis patients was berg balance scale.

Treatment protocol

Study subjects was randomly allocated to group A (Unstable surface training) and group B (Conventional exercises) to perform the intervention.

Group A: (Unstable surface training)

Unstable surface training includes the exercises on the wobble board. A wobble board, also known as a balance board, is used in physical therapy to train for balance, athletics, posture, coordination, and fall prevention. The user tries to balance on a circular item with an uneven base.

Figure 3.1: wobble board (Nilsson et al., 2012)

- **Squats:** instruct the subject to place their feet on the edge of the wobble board.

While maintaining your chest raised, bend your knees and hips to lower yourself into a squat.

- **Sit to stand:** start by sitting in the middle of the board with both feet shoulder-width apart. To stand up while keeping your balance, lean slightly forward and push through your heels. Then carefully lower yourself back to sitting posture.

Figure 3.2: Sit it to stand on wobble board

- **Forward lunges:** Instruct the patient to step one foot onto the wobble board and drop into a lunge while keeping your balance. The back knee should bend toward the floor, and the front knee should line up with the ankle.
- **Step-ups:** Step-ups on a wobble board are performed by standing facing the board and placing it on a level, non-slip surface. To raise the other foot onto the wobble board, place one foot in the middle, contract your core, and push through that foot. To keep your equilibrium, pause for a while, then carefully and slowly walk back down.

Figure 3.3: Step-up on wobble board

- **Timed single leg stance:** On a wobble board, stand with both feet on the board and slowly raise one foot off the ground to execute a timed single leg stance. Focus on a fixed spot, use your core, and maintain balance on the standing leg. Hold the position for 10 seconds, or if tolerated.
- **Wall slides:** To perform wall slides on a wobble board stand with your feet shoulder-width apart and your back to the wall. Maintain your knees over your toes and the board balanced, slowly slide down the wall into a partial squat. After a little period of holding the squat, carefully glide back up to standing.

Figure 3.4: wall slide on wobble board

All exercises will be performed 3 times a week in sessions of 4 sets for 4 weeks each, consisting of 6 repetitions and a one-minute break in between (Kotteeswaran et al., 2020).

Group B: Conventional exercises

- **Quadriceps isometric strengthening exercises:** Lying flat on your back with your legs relaxed and straight. Tighten your thigh muscle by squeezing the back of your knee against a rolled towel underneath one knee without raising the heel or shifting the leg, hold the contraction for 6 seconds. Perform 10 repetitions with 2 seconds rest interval.

Figure 3.5: Isometric quadriceps strengthening

- **Active stretching of hamstrings:** Lying on your back with one leg straight on the floor and the other leg up is an active hamstring stretch. Without using your hands, steadily raise the raised leg toward your chest using your thigh muscles while maintaining a straight posture. Maintaining the opposite leg and back flat, hold the position for 6 seconds. Perform 10 repetitions with 2 second rest intervals.

Figure 3.6: stretching of hamstrings

- **Active stretching of quadriceps:** Lying on your stomach with both legs straight is an active way to stretch your quadriceps. Using just your hamstrings and no hands, bend one leg to pull your heel closer to your buttocks. Slowly drop the leg back down after holding the position for 6 seconds. Perform 10 repetitions with 2 seconds rest interval.

Figure 3.7: stretching of quadriceps

- **Hamstring isometric strengthening exercises:** To perform a hamstring isometric strengthening exercise, lie on your back with one knee bent and foot flat on the floor. Press your heel down into the floor as if trying to slide it toward your body without moving it. Engage your hamstring muscles and hold the contraction for 6 seconds. Perform 10 repetitions with 2 seconds rest interval.

Figure 3.8: Isometric strengthening of hamstring

- **Active ankle pumps:** Rest your back with the legs at full length in order to perform the active ankle pumps. When moving your feet, toes must be lifted straight up towards the head (dorsiflexion) then straight down away (plantarflexion) away the body. Do 10 times with a 2 s rest (Chhabr & Sathya, 2015).

Figure 3.9: Active ankle pumping

3.2 Ethical Consideration

The code of ethics and guidelines set by the ethical committee of the TIMES Institute, Multan was adhered to in this research study. The well-being and the rights of the participants were given priority in the following ways. Every respondent was giving informed written consent, which stated that she/he was taking part in the study voluntarily. Strong confidentiality measures were followed to ensure that no information and data was compromised. The identities of the participants were anonymized so that they could preserve their privacy and maintain confidentiality. The participants were being fully informed of the study procedures, as well as possible risks and drawbacks of their participation in the study. Participants were retaining the right to withdraw from the study at any point without repercussion. All data be securely stored with restricted access and protected through password encryption and other measures. These steps are intended to uphold ethical research practices and protect the participant's rights and integrity throughout the study.

3.3 Plan for Data Analysis

SPSS version 26.0 was served as the tool for analyzing the data. The quantitative variable of age was displayed numerical values with mean calculations and standard deviation (mean \pm S.D). Gender information along with knee involvement side was displayed in tables and illustrated through bar and pie charts that show frequencies and percentages. The Shapiro Wilk test verified the normal distribution of data.

- The within group analysis was conducted by Paired T-Test and maintained a p-value below 0.05.
- The analysis of inter-group differences was conducted by Independent T-Test to generate results with p-value lower than 0.05.

Figure 3.8: CONSORT flow diagram showing patient exclusions for randomized clinical trial.

Chapter 4

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

The study had a total of 32 participants. Patients in group A had an average mean age of 51.33 ± 3.06 whereas those in group B had an average mean age of 54.24 ± 3.85 . Group A consisted of 9 (44%) male and 7 (56%) females, Group B contained 5 (28%) men and 11 (72 %) females, in accordance with the gender distribution that was assessed. Then the analysis was conducted within each group. Results were evaluated prior to the start of the treatment regimen and following the completion of the 4-week treatment period. Pre- and post-values were collected to check for improvement across variables.

- In group A there was a statistically significant difference in the mean BBS scores across time periods ($p = 0.001$). The results showed that the means of BBS scores increased statistically significantly from pre-intervention to post-intervention.
- In group B there was a statistically significant difference in the mean BBS scores across time periods ($p = 0.001$). The results showed that the means of BBS scores increased statistically significantly from pre-intervention to post-intervention.

Then, a between-groups analysis was performed. To determine if there had been improvements in the variable between the groups, the post-scores of the outcome measure of the two groups were computed. The two groups' means for BBS scores were compared. Post BBS mean value of group A was 46.25 ± 4.94 while post oxygen saturation mean of group B was 38.37 ± 4.57 with mean difference of 7.88 between the groups which showed that post mean value of group A showed better improvement as compared to post mean value of oxygen saturation of group B with p value less than 0.001 that was statistically significant. The result showed that unstable surface training was superior to conventional exercise program for improving balance in patients with knee osteoarthritis.

Table 4.1: Mean Age of Osteoarthritic patients in groups

Variables	Group A Mean ± S.D	Group B Mean ± S.D
Age	51.33 ± 3.06	54.24 ± 3.85

Table showed the mean age of the patients in group A and B. Participants in each group were relatively the same age. Group A had a mean age of 51.33 years with the standard deviation of 3.06 and Group B having a mean age of 54.24 years and standard deviation is 3.85 (Table 4.1).

Table 4.2: Age Distribution of Osteoarthritic patients in groups

Age Distribution in Groups				
			Group A:	Group B:
Age range	45-50	N	7	3
		%	43.80%	18.80%
	51-55	N	2	12
		%	12.50%	70.00%
	56-60	N	7	1
		%	43.80	6.30%

Result demonstrates the average mean age of patients in group A was 51.33 ± 3.06 while average mean age of patients in group B was 54.24 ± 3.85 . In group A, 7(43.80%) patients were in age range between 40-50 years. 2(12.50%) patients were having age range between 51-55 years. 7(43.80%) patients had age range between 56-60 years. In group B, 3(18.80%) patients were having age range between 45-50 years. 12 (70.00%) patients had age range between 51-55 years. 1 (6.30%) patient had age range between 56-60 years (table 4.2).

Figure 4.1: Age distributions of OA patients in group A & B

Bar chart shows the Age distribution in percentage, Age ranges 45-50 contained 43.80% patients from Group A and 18.80% from Group B. In 51-55-year, age range, there were 12.40% patients in Group A and 75.00% in Group B. In the age category of 56-60 years with Group A having 43.80% patients and 6.20% patients in Group B (Figure 4.1).

Figure 4.2: Gender distributions of OA patients

Pie chart showed the demographic indicates the gender distribution with 37 percent (n=12) male participants against 63 percent (n=20) female participants. Frequency of female participants were more than male participants (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.3: Age distributions of OA patients in Group A

Pie chart showed the demographic indicates the gender distribution in group A with 44 percent (n=9) male participants against 56 percent (n=7) female participants. Frequency of female participants were more than male participants in group A (Figure 4.2).

Figure 4.4: Age distributions of OA patients in Group B

Pie chart showed the demographic indicates the gender distribution in group B with 28 percent (n=5) male participants against 72 percent (n=11) female participants. Frequency of female participants were more than male participants in group B (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.5: Affected side of Knee OA patients

Pie chart showed the involvement of Knee in patient. According to the findings 22 (69 %) patients are affected with bilateral Knee OA and 10 (31 %) patients are affected with unilateral Knee OA were included in study (Figure 4.5).

Table 4.3: Test of Normality

Variables	Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.
Age	.975	32	.654
Pre BBS-Score	.969	32	.477
Post BBS-Score	.979	32	.764

After applying for a test of normality, data was normally distributed with significant p-value (>0.05). Parametric tests were applied. Independent samples T test was applied to find the difference between the groups (Table 4.3).

Table 4.4: Within Group Comparison of BBS Scores of Group A

Variables	Group A (n=16)			
	Pre	Post	Mean difference	P
	Mean ± S. D	Mean ± S. D		
BBS	29.502 ± 4.79	46.25 ± 4.94	16.75	0.01

A within-group analysis was carried out. Outcome assessments were taken before the treatment regimen began and after 4 weeks treatment ended. Pre and post values were taken to see if there was any improvement within variable. In group A, mean of BBS Score differed statistically significantly. The results revealed that mean of BBS Score was statistically significantly increased from pre- intervention to post intervention with P =0.01 (Table 4.4).

Figure 4.6: Within Group Comparison of Group A of Knee OA patients

Table 4.5: Within Group Comparison of BBS Score of Group B

Variables	Group B (n=16)			
	Pre	Post	Mean difference	P
	Mean ± S. D	Mean ± S. D		
BBS	34.12 ± 4.25	38.37 ± 4.57	4.25	0.01

A within-group analysis was carried out. Outcome assessments were taken before the treatment regimen began and after 4 weeks treatment ended. Pre and post values were taken to see if there was any improvement within variable. In group B mean of BBS Score differed statistically significantly. The results revealed that the BBS Score statistically significantly increased from pre- intervention to post intervention with P =0.01 (Table 4.5)

Figure 4.7: Within Group Comparison of Group B of Knee OA patients

Figure 4.8: Bar chart of Pre & Post BBS Score of Groups

Bar graph shows the findings of a paired sample t-test between Group A and Group B concerning a Pre- and Post- BBS (berg balance Scale). The mean pre-test score of Group A was 29.5 and post-test was 46.2. Group B recorded a mean score of 34.1 and 38.4 before and after the test respectively. There was an improvement in BBS scores in both groups between pre-test and post-test the paired sample t-test showed that within-group improvement in BBS score was statistically significant (Figure 4.8).

Table 4.6: Post BBS Score

Variables	Group	N	Mean± S. D	Mean Difference	P
POST BBS Score	Group A	16	46.25±4.94	7.88	.001
	Group B	16	38.37±4.57		

Mean value of BBS Score of both groups was compared. Post BBS Score mean value of group A was 46.25 ± 4.64 while post BBS Score mean of group B was 38.37 ± 4.57 with mean difference of 7.88 between the groups which showed that BBA Score post mean value of group A showed better improvement as compared to post mean value of BBS Score of group B with p value 0.001 that was statistically significant (Table 4.6).

Figure 4.9: Between Compassion of Group A & B of Knee OA patients

Mean value of BBS Score of both groups was compared. Post BBS Score mean value of group A was 46.25 while post BBS Score mean of group B was 38.37 which showed that BBA Score post mean value of group A showed better improvement as compared to post mean value of BBS Score of group B with p value 0.001 that was statistically significant (Figure 4.9).

4.2 DISCUSSION

The goal of the current study was to compare and analyze the effects of unstable surface training against conventional exercise program on balance in patient with knee osteoarthritis. The results of the present study revealed that the pre- and post-values of the outcome measure were enhanced by both training regimens. But when compared, it was found that the unstable surface training was superior to conventional exercise program for increasing balance in knee osteoarthritis (p -value < 0.001). These results imply that adding unstable surfaces to rehabilitation regimens offers a stronger incentive to improve dynamic stability and postural control in this patient group.

The researchers found no published research comparing the advantages of unstable surface training with conventional exercise program on balance in knee osteoarthritic individuals. These findings are also evinced by a parallel study by Pirayeh et al. that intended to study the overall impact of balance training on functional outcomes in a similar cohort of patients. Findings of the study were meaningful and consistent with ours. They demonstrated that a focused program of balance training dramatically improved postural stability and balance in the experimental group as compared to the control group that did not receive such kind of intervention. This piecing of evidence leads to the belief that balance-centric exercises like training on unstable surfaces, are an exceedingly useful element of therapy in improving stability in individuals with osteoarthritis in the knee. (Pirayeh et al., 2022).

The gains seen in the group that engaged in traditional exercise were expected and consistent with a strong body of research. The mainstays of treatment for knee OA include traditional exercises. Proprioceptive feedback and joint stability two crucial components of balance are enhanced by strengthening the muscles surrounding the knee. Therefore, the positive outcomes in the CE group validate that knee OA symptoms and functional limitations can be effectively treated with standard therapy. These enhancements further support the established benefits of traditional training in lowering pain, delaying functional decline, and improving mobility in this patient group. Frequent engagement in organized exercise regimens has also been linked to better gait mechanics and a lower risk of secondary issues like falls and additional joint deterioration. Crucially the consistency of these results across all patient groups emphasizes traditional exercise as a dependable

and cost-effective treatment option serving as the foundation for most evidence-based rehabilitation recommendations for knee OA. (Fransen et al., 2015).

Nonetheless, the UST group's noticeably higher gains offer strong support for the benefits of proprioceptive and neuromuscular difficulties. There are several important mechanisms that explain this superiority. First, severe proprioceptive impairments are a hallmark of knee OA in addition to articular deterioration (Shakoor et al., 2012). Wobble boards, foam pads, and balancing discs are unstable surfaces that produce a dynamic environment that constantly shifts the patient's center of gravity. The sensorimotor system must make quick unconscious modifications to keep the body balanced. Mechanoreceptors in the muscles, tendons, and joints are strongly stimulated by this process, which improves proprioceptive acuity and creates more effective neuromuscular recruitment patterns. In essence UST targets a core deficit in knee OA directly and functions as a type of "high dose" proprioceptive retraining (Hübscher et al., 2010).

The better neuromuscular control and strength along the entire kinetic chain are indicated by the UST group's increased performance. Co-contraction of the ankle, knee, hip, and core stabilizers is necessary to maintain balance on an unsteady surface. This enhances the functional strength of stabilizers such as the vastus medialis obliquus and gluteus Medius, which are essential for regulating femoral adduction and knee valgus during weight-bearing activities and encourages synergistic muscle activation. UST trains these muscles in a closed-chain, functional context that directly translates to better dynamic balance, whereas the traditional program may strengthen them in a controlled open-chain fashion (Khayambashi et al., 2012).

Filipa et al. when compared to strength training alone, a 6-week program that included balance exercises on unstable surfaces resulted in noticeably larger improvements in postural sway and functional reach. The result of this study is in conjunction with our findings and create a consistent narrative that Conventional workouts are unable to properly recreate the specific training stimulus that UST offers. The neuromuscular system seems to be challenged by the dynamic and unexpected nature of unstable situations in ways that support improved proprioceptive control, sensory integration, and adaptive motor responses. In therapeutic and rehabilitative settings where regaining stability and balance is crucial for lowering the risk of falls and enhancing general functional independence, such adaptations are crucial. As a result, the increasing amount of data

demonstrates the benefits of UST in both therapeutic and preventive settings, bolstering its inclusion as an adjunct to conventional strength and conditioning regimens (Filipa et al., 2010).

Patients with osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee can benefit from conventional exercise (CE) to improve their balance. This result seems to go against the findings of the systematic review by Behm et al. (2015), which concluded that in comparison to stable surface training (STS), strength training on unstable surfaces (STU) offered few additional benefits for strength, power, and balance in healthy adolescents and young adults. This disparity emphasizes the vital significance of population-specific prescription and the core idea of training specificity rather than indicating faulty results. Older adults and clinical groups, like those with knee OA, frequently present with proprioceptive deficits, impaired joint stability, and reduced functional mobility. However, proprioceptive acuity, balancing efficiency, and neuromuscular control may already be at their best in younger healthier individuals meaning that further benefits from UST are negligible. For these groups, UST's disruptive stimulation may be a potent therapeutic tool resulting in neuromuscular alterations that instantly improve function. Thus, the apparent contradiction with Behm et al.'s findings highlights the necessity of tailoring therapies to satisfy the target population's unique physiological and functional requirements in addition to the desired result (Behm et al., 2015).

Ince et al. undertook a study to determine the effectiveness of balance exercises and proprioception on female patients with knee OA. According to the study's findings proprioception and balance exercises can enhance dynamic balance and lessen pain.

The current study's finding corresponds with the previous studies findings, which showed that unstable surface training which a specialized type of balance training is effective in improving balance in patients with knee osteoarthritis. Unstable surface training improves the proprioception by challenging the balance of patient which deal to the activation and retraining of proprioceptors which in turn improve balance in knee osteoarthritic patients (Ince et al., 2023).

The findings of the study are immediately applicable in clinical settings. Rehabilitation professionals should consider systematically implementing unstable surface training in addition to traditional strength-focused regimens for treating knee OA. This should start with simple bilateral positions on a soft surface and progressively more difficult single leg

positions and dynamic movements on progressively more unstable apparatus. The weaknesses in the proprioception and neuromuscular control, which are uncontrollable with traditional exercise only, can be remedied with the help of UST. These treatments can be used to enhance the risk of falling, and to encourage increased mobility and independence in day-to-day activities by increasing joint stability and balance. The systematic application of UST could provide a patient-centered approach to knee OA treatment that could improve the current rehabilitation efforts.

Chapter 5

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

Summary

In short, the research focused on the relative advantages of an unstable surface training protocol and the conventional work-out program in the improvement of balance in osteoarthritic knee patients. It was found that both intervention strategies did lead to significant improvement in balance outcome compared to baseline but the group that undertook unstable surface training demonstrated better balance outcome than the control group. Training on unstable surface, wobble boards, introduces special neuromuscular challenges, which are believed to be the reason behind this greater effectiveness. These conditions result in persistent mechanical stimulation causing displacement of the center of gravity in the patient leading to high proprioceptive stimulation. The sensorimotor system then must enhance the processing of the afferent signals of the joint mechanoreceptors and respond with prompt compensating efferent commands to maintain the postural control. This approach directly targets the major proprioceptive deficiencies and atrogenic muscular inhibition that characterize impairments in the population with osteoarthritis in the knee. Strength training in the form of conventional exercise is an effective improvement of muscular strength and general functioning. It cannot however, mimic the level of neuromuscular activation and reactive control needed to handle unforeseen disruptions in day-to-day living. Co-contraction of agonist and antagonist muscle groups is encouraged by the unstable environment, which improves functional strength and dynamic joint stability when bearing weight. Additionally, accomplishing increasingly difficult tasks on unstable surfaces might boost balance. Unstable surface training should be applied gradually, starting with bilateral stances and progressing to more vigorous unilateral motions. In conclusion, unstable surface training is an extremely effective targeted intervention to assist individuals with osteoarthritis of the knee to restore their functional balance. It is to be considered as a significant component of a comprehensive rehabilitation paradigm that should be directed on enhancing the quality of life, pain alleviation, and decrease fear of falls.

Conclusion

This paper was able to conclude that both conventional exercise (CE) interventions and unstable surface training (UST) are effective interventions to improve balance in patients

with osteoarthritis (OA) of the knee, but that UST yields significantly superior improvements. The greater increase in balance of the UST group indicates its greater capability to manage the underlying neuromuscular impairments of knee OA e.g., inadequate sensorimotor control, proprioceptive impairment and quadriceps inhibition. In addition to what can be achieved through conventional strength-based training programs, UST provides a high-intensity stimulus, which effectively promotes neuromuscular change, reactive postural control, and functional joint stability by injecting unpredictable perturbations in a controlled way. These results suggest that UST ought to be included in knee OA rehabilitation to enhance balance performance, reduce fall risk, and the total extent of functional independence of the population.

5.1. IMPLIMENTATION OF STUDY

- The results back up the inclusion of UST in routine knee OA rehabilitation programs. It stresses developing neuromuscular control and proprioception alongside strength and flexibility.
- UST might be a better way to lower the risk of falls because balance issues in knee OA increase the risk of falls particularly in older persons.
- UST can be safely used to increase patient's functional mobility and independence in day-to-day living if balance improves without exacerbating joint pain or stiffness.
- Physical therapists may need to incorporate balance tools such as wobble boards, foam pads, or Bosu balls, progressing from stable to more dynamic surfaces.

5.2. LIMITATIONS

- the inability to blind therapists and participants which might have resulted in performance bias.
- While improvements in balance measurements were observed, it was not evaluated if these changes translated into actual fall reduction or patient-reported outcomes.
- Exercise dose in the unstable surface training (UST) group was not standardized
- the lack of long-term follow-up hindered knowledge of benefit retention. Generalizability to severe instances or individuals with comorbidities was limited because the sample was limited to patients with mild-to-moderate knee OA.
- The underlying causes of UST's superiority are left up for speculation because no mechanistic data (such as EMG, proprioception testing, or MRI) were gathered.

5.3. RECOMMENDATION

- Long-term follow-ups (6 months to 2 years) should be a part of future studies to evaluate the sustainability of UST benefits. Studies should also investigate ways to enhance patient adherence in community and home environments.
- In a bid to ensure maximum effectiveness and safety, further research is required to determine the optimal dose of UST based on frequency, duration, session, and progression type and tailored to different stages of knee OA.
- The synergistic effects of UST in conjunction with other evidence-based therapies, such as manual therapy, neuromuscular electrical stimulation (NMES) for quadriceps activation.
- Future research should place a high priority on monitoring psychological consequences because of the substantial correlation between balance impairment and fear of falling.
- To determine whether UST-related balance improvements indeed result in a quantifiable decrease in fall incidence among this high-risk population, large-scale, long-term randomized controlled trials with sufficient sample sizes are required.

Chapter 6

REFERENCES

- Behm, D. G., Muehlbauer, T., Kibele, A., & Granacher, U. (2015). Effects of strength training using unstable surfaces on strength, power and balance performance across the lifespan: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sports Medicine*, 45, 1645-1669. DOI 10.1007/s40279-015-0384-x
- Braghin, R. d. M. B., Libardi, E. C., Junqueira, C., Nogueira-Barbosa, M. H., & de Abreu, D. C. C. (2018). Exercise on balance and function for knee osteoarthritis: A randomized controlled trial. *Journal of bodywork and movement therapies*, 22(1), 76-82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbmt.2017.04.006>
- Chhabr, H. K., & Sathya, P. (2015). Effect of conventional exercises with balance training & only conventional exercises in patients with osteoarthritis of knee. *Int J Innov Res Sci Eng*, 4(7), 5048-5056. DOI:10.15680/IJRSET.2015.0407003
- Downs, S. (2015). The berg balance scale. *Journal of physiotherapy*, 61(1), 46. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jphys.2014.10.002>
- Elsheikh, M. M. A., El-Hawa, M. A. A., El-saadany, H. M., & Elsergany, M. (2020). The Effect of Balance Training in Knee Osteoarthritis. *Adv Med Sci*, 246-255. DOI: 10.9734/JAMMR/2020/v32i2430775
- Fawzy, A. M., Al-Hamaky, D. M. A., Ayad, K. E., Mohammed, H. A., & Abdelsalam, M. S. (2025). Effects of Instability Resistance Training on Balance and Physical Function in Patients with Chronic Knee Osteoarthritis: A Randomized Clinical Trial. *Cuestiones de Fisioterapia*, 54(2), 3908-3933. *Cuest.fisioter.* 2025.54(2):3908-3933
- Jahanjoo, F., Eftekharsadat, B., Bihamta, A., & Babaei-Ghazani, A. (2019). Efficacy of balance training in combination with physical therapy in rehabilitation of knee osteoarthritis: A randomized clinical trial. *Crescent J Med Biol Sci*, 6(3), 225

- Jeong, H. S., Lee, S.-C., Jee, H., Song, J. B., Chang, H. S., & Lee, S. Y. (2019). Proprioceptive training and outcomes of patients with knee osteoarthritis: a meta-analysis of randomized controlled trials. *Journal of athletic training*, 54(4), 418-428. <https://doi.org/10.4085/1062-6050-329-17>
- Kaur, D. (2022). Comparison of the Effect on Balance Training with Foam Balance Activity and Tilt Board Exercise to Improve Fall Risk among Physically Active Chronic Knee Osteoarthritis Patients in Selected Places of Bengaluru. *Indian Journal of Physiotherapy & Occupational Therapy*, 16(3). <https://doi.org/10.37506/ijpot.v16i3.18399>
- Koch, M., Sarma, P. C., Dutta, A., & Kalita, A. (2022). Effectiveness of Combined Kinetic Chain Exercises In the Treatment of Knee Osteoarthritis in Peri-Menopausal and Post-Menopausal Women in Guwahati, Assam, India.(2022). *Int. J. Life Sci. Pharma Res*, 12(1), L38-46. doi 10.22376/ijpbs/lpr.2022.12.1. L38-46
- Kotteeswaran, K., Sindhura, P., Sesikiran, P. M., & Manoharan, V. S. (2020). A comparative study to find the effectiveness of weight bearing exercises on stable platform versus wobble board, to improve balance and functional outcome of individuals with knee osteoarthritis. *Biomedicine*, 40(3), 381-385.
- Levinger, P., Dunn, J., Bifera, N., Butson, M., Elias, G., & Hill, K. D. (2017). High-speed resistance training and balance training for people with knee osteoarthritis to reduce falls risk: study protocol for a pilot randomized controlled trial. *Trials*, 18, 1-11. DOI 10.1186/s13063-017-2129-7
- Lim, W. B., & Al-Dadah, O. (2022). Conservative treatment of knee osteoarthritis: A review of the literature. *World journal of orthopedics*, 13(3), 212. <https://doi.org/10.5312/wjo.v13.i3.212>
- Liu, C., Wan, Q., Zhou, W., Feng, X., & Shang, S. (2017). Factors associated with balance function in patients with knee osteoarthritis: An integrative review. *International journal of nursing sciences*, 4(4), 402-409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2017.09.002>

- Luyten, F., Bierma-Zeinstra, S., Dell'Accio, F., Kraus, V., Nakata, K., Sekiya, I., Arden, N., & Lohmander, L. (2018). Toward classification criteria for early osteoarthritis of the knee. *Seminars in arthritis and rheumatism*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semarthrit.2017.08.006>
- Lv, Z., Yang, Y. X., Li, J., Fei, Y., Guo, H., Sun, Z., Lu, J., Xu, X., Jiang, Q., & Ikegawa, S. (2021). Molecular classification of knee osteoarthritis. *Frontiers in cell and developmental biology*, *9*, 725568. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fcell.2021.725568>
- Mat, S., Tan, M. P., Kamaruzzaman, S. B., & Ng, C. T. (2014). Physical therapies for improving balance and reducing falls risk in osteoarthritis of the knee: a systematic review. *Age and ageing*, *44*(1), 16-24. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afu112>
- Ni, X., Hu, L., Zhang, X., Wang, Z., Yan, C., Peyrodie, L., Lin, M., Wu, X., Wang, H., & Hu, S. (2024). Physical therapy options for knee osteoarthritis: A review. *Medicine*, *103*(30), e38415. DOI: 10.1097/MD.00000000000038415
- Park, H. J., Ko, S., Hong, H. M., Ok, E., & Lee, J. I. (2013). Factors related to standing balance in patients with knee osteoarthritis. *Annals of rehabilitation medicine*, *37*(3), 373. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5535/arm.2013.37.3.373>
- Pirayeh, N., Kazemi, K., Rahimi, F., Mostafaei, N., & Shaterzadeh-Yazdi, M.-J. (2022). The effect of balance training on functional outcomes in patients with knee osteoarthritis: a systematic review. *Medical journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*, *36*, 107. <https://doi.org/10.47176/mjiri.36.107>
- Prabhakar, A. J., Shruthi, R., Thomas, D. T., Nayak, P., Joshua, A. M., Prabhu, S., & Kamat, Y. D. (2023). Effectiveness of balance training on pain and functional outcomes in knee osteoarthritis: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *F1000Research*, *11*, 598. <https://doi.org/10.12688/f1000research.111998.2>
- Tirasci, E., Sarpel, T., Coskun Benlidayi, I., & Deniz, V. (2024). The effect of balance exercises on central sensitization in patients with knee osteoarthritis. *Rheumatology International*, *44*(5), 795-804. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00296-024-05550->

- Al-Khlaifat, L., Herrington, L. C., Tyson, S. F., Hammond, A., & Jones, R. K. (2016). The effectiveness of an exercise programme on dynamic balance in patients with medial knee osteoarthritis: A pilot study. *The Knee*, 23(5), 849-856.
- Ashtiani, A., Akbari, N. J., Mohammadi, M., & Nouraisarjou, S. (2018). The effect of balance exercises on knee instability and pain intensity in patients with knee osteoarthritis: a randomized clinical trial. *J Res Med Dent Sci*, 6(2), 74-82.
- Barr, A. J. (2016). *The role of subchondral bone in osteoarthritis* University of Leeds].
- Behm, D. G., Muehlbauer, T., Kibele, A., & Granacher, U. (2015). Effects of strength training using unstable surfaces on strength, power and balance performance across the lifespan: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Sports Medicine*, 45(12), 1645-1669.
- Coryell, P. R., Diekman, B. O., & Loeser, R. F. (2021). Mechanisms and therapeutic implications of cellular senescence in osteoarthritis. *Nature Reviews Rheumatology*, 17(1), 47-57.
- Elsheikh, M. M. A., El-Hawa, M. A. A., El-saadany, H. M., & Elsergany, M. A. E. S. (2020). The Effect of Balance Training in Knee Osteoarthritis. *Journal of Advances in Medicine and Medical Research*, 32(24), 246-255.
- Ershad, N., Kahrizi, S., Parnianpour, M., Azghani, M. R., & Khalaf, K. (2022). Trunk muscle activity during holding two types of dynamic loads in subjects with nonspecific low back pain. *Journal of bodywork and movement therapies*, 31, 7-15.
- Filipa, A., Byrnes, R., Paterno, M. V., Myer, G. D., & Hewett, T. E. (2010). Neuromuscular training improves performance on the star excursion balance test in young female athletes. *Journal of Orthopaedic & Sports Physical Therapy*, 40(9), 551-558.
- Fransen, M., McConnell, S., Harmer, A. R., Van der Esch, M., Simic, M., & Bennell, K. L. (2015). Exercise for osteoarthritis of the knee: a Cochrane systematic review. *British journal of sports medicine*, 49(24), 1554-1557.
- Giri, S., & Tewari, R. P. (2024). Alterations of generic musculoskeletal models to incorporate realistic knee joint and muscle geometry for biomechanical analyses during healthy gait: A narrative literature review. *International Journal of Biomedical Engineering and Technology*, 46(3), 180-209.
- Greco, N., Onisto, M., & Alibardi, L. (2023). Protein extracts from regenerating lizard tail show an inhibitory effect on human cancer cells cultivated in-vitro. *Annals of Anatomy-Anatomischer Anzeiger*, 250, 152115.
- Hatfield, G. L., Morrison, A., Wenman, M., Hammond, C. A., & Hunt, M. A. (2016). Clinical

- tests of standing balance in the knee osteoarthritis population: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Physical therapy*, 96(3), 324-337.
- Hübscher, M., Zech, A., Pfeifer, K., Hänsel, F., Vogt, L., & Banzer, W. (2010). Neuromuscular training for sports injury prevention: a systematic review. *Medicine & Science in Sports & Exercise*, 42(3), 413-421.
- Ince, B., Goksel Karatepe, A., Akcay, S., & Kaya, T. (2023). The efficacy of balance and proprioception exercises in female patients with knee osteoarthritis: A randomized controlled study. *Clinical Rehabilitation*, 37(1), 60-71.
- Javed, S., Riaz, H., Saeed, A., & Begum, R. (2021). Effects of biodex balance training on symptomatic knee osteoarthritis in Rawalpindi: A randomized control trial. *JPMA*, 71(2), 402-405.
- Kalpana, V., & Kumar, G. H. (2023). Evaluating the efficacy of deep learning models for knee osteoarthritis prediction based on Kellgren-Lawrence grading system. *e-Prime-Advances in Electrical Engineering, Electronics and Energy*, 5, 100266.
- Khayambashi, K., Mohammadkhani, Z., Ghaznavi, K., Lyle, M. A., & Powers, C. M. (2012). The effects of isolated hip abductor and external rotator muscle strengthening on pain, health status, and hip strength in females with patellofemoral pain: a randomized controlled trial. *Journal of Orthopaedic & Sports Physical Therapy*, 42(1), 22-29.
- Kim, D., Park, G., Kuo, L.-T., & Park, W. (2018). The effects of pain on quadriceps strength, joint proprioception and dynamic balance among women aged 65 to 75 years with knee osteoarthritis. *BMC geriatrics*, 18(1), 245.
- Kolasinski, S. L., Neogi, T., Hochberg, M. C., Oatis, C., Guyatt, G., Block, J., Callahan, L., Copenaver, C., Dodge, C., & Felson, D. (2020). 2019 American College of Rheumatology/Arthritis Foundation guideline for the management of osteoarthritis of the hand, hip, and knee. *Arthritis & rheumatology*, 72(2), 220-233.
- Kuru Çolak, T., Kavlak, B., Aydoğdu, O., Şahin, E., Acar, G., Demirbüken, İ., Sarı, Z., Çolak, İ., Bulut, G., & Polat, M. G. (2017). The effects of therapeutic exercises on pain, muscle strength, functional capacity, balance and hemodynamic parameters in knee osteoarthritis patients: a randomized controlled study of supervised versus home exercises. *Rheumatology International*, 37(3), 399-407.
- Nilsson, N. C., Serafin, S., & Nordahl, R. (2012). Gameplay as a source of intrinsic motivation for individuals in need of ankle training or rehabilitation. *Presence*, 21(1), 69-84.
- Pirayeh, N., Kazemi, K., Rahimi, F., Mostafaei, N., & Shaterzadeh-Yazdi, M.-J. (2022). The

- effect of balance training on functional outcomes in patients with knee osteoarthritis: a systematic review. *Medical journal of the Islamic Republic of Iran*, 36, 107.
- Scanzello, C. R., & Goldring, S. R. (2012). The role of synovitis in osteoarthritis pathogenesis. *Bone*, 51(2), 249-257.
- Shakoor, N., Lee, K. J., Fogg, L. F., Wimmer, M. A., Foucher, K. C., Mikolaitis, R. A., & Block, J. A. (2012). The relationship of vibratory perception to dynamic joint loading, radiographic severity, and pain in knee osteoarthritis. *Arthritis & Rheumatism*, 64(1), 181-186.
- Wang, T., & He, C. (2018). Pro-inflammatory cytokines: The link between obesity and osteoarthritis. *Cytokine & growth factor reviews*, 44, 38-50.
- Wang, X., Chen, Z., Liang, Y., Su, H., Wang, T., Lv, Y., & Yu, L. (2025). Effects of Exercise on Balance Function in People with Knee Osteoarthritis: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Randomized Controlled Trials. *Healthcare*,
- Yang, C.-Y., Chanalaris, A., & Troeberg, L. (2017). ADAMTS and ADAM metalloproteinases in osteoarthritis-looking beyond the 'usual suspects'. *Osteoarthritis and cartilage*, 25(7), 1000-1009.
- Zeng, Z., Shan, J., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y., Li, C., Li, J., Chen, W., Ye, Z., Ye, X., & Chen, Z. (2022). Asymmetries and relationships between muscle strength, proprioception, biomechanics, and postural stability in patients with unilateral knee osteoarthritis. *Frontiers in Bioengineering and Biotechnology*, 10, 922832.
- Friedman, L. M., Furberg, C. D., DeMets, D. L., Reboussin, D. M., & Granger, C. B. (2015). *Fundamentals of clinical trials*. Springer.
- Elfil, M., & Negida, A. (2017). Sampling methods in clinical research; an educational review. *Emergency*, 5(1), e52.
- Lindley, R. I., & Mangin, D. (2023). Deprescribing to optimise health outcomes for frail older people: a double-blind placebo-controlled randomised controlled trial—outcomes of the Opti-med study. *Age and ageing*, 52(5), afad081.
- A. E., Vollset, S. E., & Brooks, P. M. (2023). Global, regional, and national burden of osteoarthritis, 1990-2020 and projections to 2050: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021. *The Lancet Rheumatology*, 5(9), e508-e522.

APPENDIX A

CONSENT FORM

The study you are about to participate is a randomized clinical trial survey titled as;

**“Comparative Analysis of Unstable Surface Training and Conventional Exercises on
Balance in Knee Osteoarthritis”**

The study has no potential harm to participants. All data collected from you will be coded in order to protect your identity, and should not be disclosed to anyone. Following the study there will be no way to connect your name with your data. Your answers to the questions will not affect the quality of education given to you. Any additional information about the study results will be provided to you at its conclusion, upon your request.

You are free to withdraw from the study at any time. You agree to participate, indicating that you have read and understood the nature of the study, and that all your inquiries concerning the activities have been answered to your satisfaction.

NAME: _____

SIGNATURE: _____

DATE: _____

BERG BALANCE TEST

Name: _____ Date: _____

Age: _____ Sex: _____ Diagnosis: _____

Contact no.: _____ Address: _____

Location: _____ Rater: _____

S.N.	Item Description	Date			
		Score [0-4]			
1	Sit to stand				
2	Standing Unsupported				
3	Sitting Unsupported				
4	Standing to sitting				
5	Transfers				
6	Standing with eyes closed				
7	Standing with feet together				
8	Reaching forward with outstretched arms				
9	Retrieving object from ground				
10	Turning to look behind				
11	Turning 360 degrees				
12	Placing alternate foot on stool				
13	Standing with one foot in front				
14	Standing on one foot				
	Total				

Interpretation

- 0-20 : Wheelchair bound
- 21-40 : Walking with assistance
- 41-56 : Independent

SIGNATURES

Internship / Project Supervisory Committee Signature

Supervisor	
Convener	
Member 1	
Member 2	
Member 3	
Member 4	
Subject Expert	
Deputy Controller of Examinations	

Exam Receiving

Received By	
Received On	

